

D8.3.1

The improved Open Energy Platform

WITH LESS BUGS, MORE SECURITY AND INCREASED USABILITY

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The OEP Improved

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General Information

Summary

This deliverable contains links to the results of the FlexFund project “Open Energy Platform Improved: More security, less bugs, more usability”

This FlexFund project thus aimed at eradicating security issues and bugs and to improve usability of the OEP. The deliverable, an improved Open Energy Platform, will be able to attract more users from the German energy systems modelling community and beyond.

Why is this deliverable is needed:

Energy scenarios are complex heterogeneous data structures. Their interoperability plays a key role in the traceability, transparency and comparability in energy research. If energy scenarios are documented in a standardised way and the various components are published FAIR, working with them becomes more efficient, transparent and reproducible. This is a benefit for research, which can become more efficient and transparent as a result. In addition, interoperability increases. Against the backdrop of the increasingly urgent need to tackle the climate crisis, speed is of the essence. This applies not only to action, but also to research and the data that informs those taking action. The OEP as a data infrastructure on which high-quality interoperable scenario data can be published, found, compared and reused, in a comprehensible manner, is therefore a central element for faster and legally compliant utilisation of data.

Key developments of the OEP took place between 2018 and 2021 in the [Energieforschungsprogramm](#) projects [SzenarienDB](#) and [SIROP](#). Development took place [open source on github](#) at all times, which also means that it may happen that bugs and usability hurdles are online and users of the OEP face these. After SIROP the OEP is now at a stage where several key functionalities (services of the [Open Energy Family](#)) are available to support and enhance energy systems research.

At the same time, security issues, bugs and usability issues still pose hurdles towards a broader adoption of the OEP in the community.

Unfortunately, funding for projects that have dedicated time for developing the OEP further came to an end in 2024, while there were security and usability issues and bugs present that pose hurdles for wider adoption of the platform.

Deliverable within NFDI4Energy

Our FlexFund project aimed to improve the Open Energy Platform, so that it will be usable by a broader audience within the energy systems modelling research domain. The work was located in Task Area 8: Data and Core Services. This Task Area focuses on the service development within NFDI4Energy, the development of core services as well as adapting and improving service based on community and consortia feedback.

The Open Energy Platform is a core service.

We thus focused on making it fit(ter) for purpose. We identified issues that are of relevance for better use – this included a focus on security, bugs and usability. After identifying issues in these key areas, we prioritized them for systematically solving them within the lifetime of the project.

The projects lifetime was March 2025 – December 2025.

The deliverable itself is an improved version of the Open Energy Platform.

The version of the platform at the end of the project is available here:

<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/releases/tag/v1.6.2>

Deliverable

At the beginning of the project, we dedicated time to identify security, bug and usability issues. We tagged them accordingly for better categorization.

Working on the improvement of the OEP started right away. On July 8, 2025 we met and prioritized the NFDI4Energy issues created until then. Further implementation proceeded according to the prioritization list.

While the work on these issues was priority, in parallel, new issues were created so as to keep track on further enhancements that could either be tackled within this project or taken on by follow-up projects.

At the End of the projects lifetime we delivered an improved version of the Open Energy Platform. The latest version released by the project can be found here:

<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/releases/tag/v1.6.2>

Summary of the issues (closed / total):

- NFDI-FlexFundSecurity: (4/5) - <https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/issues?q=is%3Aissue%20label%3ANFDI%20%20FlexFundSecurity>
- NFDI-FlexFundBug: (40/50) - <https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/issues?q=is%3Aissue%20label%3ANFDI-FlexFundBug>
- NFDI-FlexFundUsability (25/59) - <https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/issues?q=is%3Aissue%20label%3ANFDI%20%20FlexFundUsability>

Several releases led to the improved Open Energy Platform. These are listed below, with short summaries and links to the release and its corresponding changelog.

Release 1.6.2 – January 7, 2026

The final release for the project was dedicated to enhance the CSV upload tool. It also fixed various bugs concerning the metadata builder tool, the scenario bundles and factsheets. Caching issues were fixed and a bug that lost table filter options when navigation across paginated result pages was fixed.

<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/releases/tag/v1.6.2>

Changelog:

https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/blob/master/versions/changelogs/1_6_2.md

Release 1.6.1 - January 7, 2026

This release includes enhanced security in the advanced API.

References to the outdated scenario bundles URL linked from OEP homepage tile were repaired.

<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/releases/tag/v1.6.1>

Changelog:

https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/blob/master/versions/changelogs/1_6_1.md

Release 1.6.0 – November 27, 2025

The highlights of this release were that API and database URLs are now streamlined: The Rest-API and frontend URLs, while the use of old URL patterns are redirected to the new patterns.

Columns in the dataview are now ordered by their ordinal position, starting with "id" column.

The datatable views now have the functioning feature to plot spatial data with lat/long coordinates.

<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/releases/tag/v1.6.0>

Changelog:

https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/blob/master/versions/changelogs/1_6_0.md

Release 1.5.2 – October 30, 2025

This release improved the way tables are displayed by adding pagination, the possibility to sort by creation date and the added feature to unpublish tables. On the frontend, the messaging system was harmonised. The oeo view app is now able to use the TIB-Terminology Service API to query the OEO contents.

<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/releases/tag/v1.5.2>

Changelog:

https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/blob/master/versions/changelogs/1_5_2.md

Release 1.5.1 – October 25, 2025

The tag system was moved from OEDB to Djangos internal DB, so that primary and application databases could be fully decoupled. The OEO-Viewer was reworked based on the TIB-Terminology Service and – Suite.

Various bugs were fixed, including the error display system, the rendering of the data preview when invalid JSON data is present and the rendering of data preview when infinity values are present.

<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/releases/tag/v1.5.1>

Changelog:

https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/blob/master/versions/changelogs/1_5_1.md

Release 1.5.0 – October 23, 2025

This release focused on implementing the long time planned update to the primary database setup (OEDB) and its effect on the Database access layer implemented in the oeplatform. This makes the architecture more clean and decouples the large volume data storage from the application. To get there, we condensed all physical database schemas to a single "data" schema on the OEDB. In the application we still use the schemas as topics but now they purely are used to group the data for

presentation. Managing data resources and synchronizing the app and oedb data becomes way more straight forward.

<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/releases/tag/v1.5.0>

Changelog:

https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/blob/master/versions/changelogs/1_5_0.md

Hotfix 1.4.1 - October 9, 2025

This release fixed a bug that prevented the functionality that multiple users can edit a scenario bundle to work properly.

<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/releases/tag/v1.4.1>

Changelog:

https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/blob/master/versions/changelogs/1_4_1.md

Release 1.4.0 - September 17, 2025

This release includes major updates on scenario bundles and the Open Peer Review process as well as bug fixes and achieved stability increases. The peer review is now fully aligned with the OEMetadata Standard v2 and the scenario bundles were upgraded to OEKG v2 which results in faster page loads and a more stable back- and frontend.

<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/releases/tag/v1.4.0>

Changelog:

https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/blob/master/versions/changelogs/1_4_0.md

Hotfix 1.3.4 – September 17, 2025

This hotfix added a new feature: REST API to receive all and specific table metadata on data size

<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/releases/tag/v1.3.4>

Changelog:

https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/blob/master/versions/changelogs/1_3_4.md

Hotfix 1.3.3 - July 17, 2025

This hotfix was dedicated to bugs and hence usability: Most notably for users: the captcha in the contact form did not work correctly and now does.

<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/releases/tag/v1.3.3>

Changelog:

https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/blob/master/versions/changelogs/1_3_3.md

Patch 1.3.2 - July 10, 2025

This hotfix was dedicated to the Meta Information section, and added a dropdown button to either download the oemetadata.json file or view the oemetadata api page for the specific table

<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/releases/tag/v1.3.2>

Changelog:

https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/blob/master/versions/changelogs/1_3_2.md

Patch 1.3.1 – July 10, 2025

This release brings REUSE compliance and dataset import enhancements.

<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/releases/tag/v1.3.1>

Changelog:

https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/blob/master/versions/changelogs/1_3_1.md

Release 1.3.0 - June 11, 2025

This release brings improvements for the developers (docker-based development setup), enhancements in usability such as a better navigation bar, improved scenario bundle usability as well as bug fixes such as making the scenario bundle filters behave correctly.

<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/releases/tag/v1.3.0>

Changelog:

https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/blob/master/versions/changelogs/1_3_0.md

Hotfix 1.2.3 - May 5, 2025

This is a hotfix that relates to fixing bugs in the metadata builder that showed some unexpected behaviour. For example, proper titles were added when default category titles are used, category tabs which are not shown in the schema but were still visible on the website were removed.

<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/releases/tag/v1.2.3>

Changelog:

https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/blob/master/versions/changelogs/1_2_3.md

Hotfix 1.2.2 - April 3, 2025

This hotfix fixed display issues in some section titles when using the oemetaBuilder online.

<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/releases/tag/v1.2.2>

Changelog:

https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/blob/master/versions/changelogs/1_2_2.md

Hotfix Release 1.2.1 – April 3, 2025

This hotfix added a temporary banner to the OEP landing page informing about the OEMetadata v.2.0.4 release

<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/releases/tag/v1.2.1>

Changelog:

https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform/blob/master/versions/changelogs/1_2_1.md